

INFLUENCE OF GLASS TRANSITION TEMPERATURE OF THERMOPLASTIC AND THERMOSET LAMINATES ON THEIR FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR

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1 Introduction

Nowadays, TP-based laminates are becoming more and more attractive to the industry, because of promising alternatives compared to TS matrix composites, especially with their reduced curing time and their recycling properties. However, further growth of TP-based composites is directly linked to the knowledge of their long-term behaviour (fatigue and creep). Lately, a few authors have investigated the fatigue behaviour of TP-based laminates [1-4], but very few references are available in the literature about the fatigue behaviour of PMCs when temperature is higher than the glass transition temperature T_g .

For woven-ply laminates, failure is usually initiated by cracks in weft fibre bundles, which subsequently grow either into matrix-rich areas or into the interface between longitudinal/ transverse fibre bundles within the same layer (the so-called meta-delamination), and ultimately fibre breakage [5]. Besides, the fatigue behaviour is strongly influenced by the ductility of the matrix. Indeed, the distribution of the matrix in woven-ply laminates initially results from the non-planar interply structure of woven plies, in which the weft fibre bundles undulate over the warp fibre bundles according to a given weave pattern [6]. An interlaminar crack will interact with matrix regions and the weave structure during its propagation, resulting in substantial crack growth resistance and a better resistance to delamination [7]. The concept of introducing soft regions, sometimes referred to as softening strips, into a fibre composite to provide barriers to crack growth and so raise the intrinsic toughness of the material has been well established [8] [9]. From the fatigue performances standpoint, it is therefore potentially interesting to associate woven fabrics with highly ductile thermoplastic matrices [10] [1], which effect is even more noticeable when service temperature is

higher than the material glass transition temperature [11].

The present work was therefore aimed at studying the fatigue behaviour of woven-ply TP- and TS-based laminates at a service temperature T such as: $T_g|_{C/PPS} < T < T_g|_{Epoxy}$. The objective of this paper is to understand to what extent the matrix behaviour and the angled ply (45°) contributes to the fatigue behaviour and the damage accumulation during fatigue tests in QI laminates at different test frequencies. Indeed, because of the non-planar structure of the woven reinforcement, microscopic observations of laminates edges show lots of matrix-rich regions (see Fig.1) which seem to be instrumental in ruling the fatigue behaviour of PMCs.

Fig.1. Edges microscopic observations of QI C/PPS laminates showing lots of matrix-rich regions

2 Materials, experimental set-up and objectives

The studied composite materials are carbon fabric reinforced laminates consisting of two different matrices: a semi-crystalline high-performance PPS (TP) and an amorphous Epoxy one (TS). The toughened PPS resin and epoxy resin are respectively supplied by the Ticona and Hexcel company. The woven-ply prepreg consists of 5-harness satin weave carbon fibre fabrics (T300 3K 5HS). The volume fraction of fibres is 50% in both laminates. A DMTA analysis showed that the glass transition temperature is 95°C in C/PPS [12],

whereas it is 190°C in C/Epoxy. The prepreg plates are hot pressed according to two lay-ups:

- Quasi-isotropic (QI)
[(0,90)/(±45)/(0,90)/(±45)/(0,90)/(±45)/(0,90)]
- Angle-ply (AP) [(±45)]₇

This QI sequence is commonly used for applications in aircraft nacelles in the case of TS-based composites.

Fatigue tests were performed using a 100kN capacity load cell of an MTS 810 servo-hydraulic testing machine. Tests were conducted at two frequencies (1Hz and 10 Hz) and at 120°C. It's worth noticing that the aircraft nacelle's service temperature $T = 120^{\circ}\text{C}$. Both materials were tested according to two stacking sequences, and for different stress levels:

- For QI: 70, 80, 90% of σ_u
- For AP: 50, 60, 70% of σ_u

All Fatigue tests were performed at a stabilized ratio $R = \sigma_{min}/\sigma_{max} = 0$. Temperature was monitored at the surface of specimens throughout tests, in order to observe the effect of both frequency and stress level on autogeneous heating resulting. In addition, a fractography analysis (Scanning Electron Microscope and Optical Microscope observation of failed specimens) was conducted in order to understand the fatigue damage mechanisms related to each material.

3 Angle-ply laminates

3.1 General standpoint

Nearly, all multi-directional laminates contain a considerable fraction of $[\pm 45^{\circ}]$ angle-ply reinforcement layers to bear shear loads, to control stress concentrations and the damage behaviour [13]. A crucial role is thereby taken over by the $[\pm 45^{\circ}]$ layers, making relevant to initially consider the fatigue behaviour of A-P laminates [5] [14]. The mechanical properties and the monotonic behaviour of the materials have been studied in a previous work [15]. C/PPS laminates' response to off-axis monotonic loadings has proved to be highly ductile and time-dependent at 120°C [15] [16], contrary to C/Epoxy laminates [15]. From a general standpoint, frequency virtually does not influence the fatigue life of C/PPS laminates, whereas it dramatically decreases the fatigue life (-100%) of Epoxy-based laminates, particularly as applied stress increases (See Fig.2).

Fig.2. Influence of frequency on fatigue life of A-P laminates subjected to fatigue tensile loadings at 120°C

Both materials have the same reinforcement, but differ from the nature of their matrix. It confirms that plasticity and viscous effects influence the fatigue behaviour of polymer-based laminates. Besides, a significant autogeneous heating has been observed on specimen surface at high frequency and high applied stress. A temperature gradient increase of 80°C and 55°C has been monitored in C/PPS and C/Epoxy respectively. Such an increase is of the utmost importance because it can lead to a softening of the material and to a premature failure.

Fig.3. Comparison of the hysteresis loops depending on the test frequency at 80% of fatigue life and at 60% σ_u - (a) C/PPS - (b) C/Epoxy

3.2 Fatigue behaviour: Analysis of the hysteresis loops' shape

During a fatigue test as well as during a monotonic test, the specimen's deformation may come along

with a plasticization of the pure-matrix region allowing the fibres to rotate, depending on matrix ductility. Such phenomenon can be observed by comparing the shape of hysteresis loop found during a fatigue test at 60% σ_u and 80% of fatigue life (see Fig.3.)

C/PPS laminates display “banana” shaped loops consisting of two parts. The first part of the loop is related to the loading phase during which the large rotation of fibres comes along with the large plastic deformation of PPS matrix mostly in matrix-rich regions (See Fig.3-a). More precisely, phase 1 and 2 (see Fig.4.) correspond respectively to the elastic response followed by matrix plasticization. A secondary stiffening associated with the locking of rotating fibres (Phase 3 – See Fig.4) can be observed on the C/PPS loops from stresses reaching 40% of σ_u (See black dotted lines on Fig.3a). It suggests that there is a threshold orientation from which laminates regain stiffness and start damaging. The second part is related to the unloading phase (Phase 4 – See Fig.4) during which fibres disorientate, and the opening of the loops seems to be ascribed to the viscoelastic behaviour (even more noticeable at low frequency). C/Epoxy laminates display loops whose shapes are either an elongated ellipse at 10Hz or a crushed ellipse at 1Hz (See Fig.3b). For both frequencies, the loops shape reveal reduced fibres rotations (lower than 5°) and damage accumulation which are consistent with the low ductility of epoxy matrix during loading phase. In addition, secondary stiffening is not observed on C/epoxy loops because fibres rotation is reduced during loading phase, hence justifying that fibres disorientation is reduced, and the viscoelastic response of the matrix is minimized during the unloading phase.

Fig.4. Different phases of the mechanical response of laminates subjected to tensile loading (a) and unloading (b) at 120°

3.3 Damage accumulation concept

In order to evaluate the damage accumulation during fatigue tests, a damage variable based on the features of the stress-strain loops during cyclic loadings can be defined. Classically, the change in longitudinal stiffness that occurs during cycling is used to evaluate the accumulated damage [17]. However, the measured dynamic stiffness is not a good indicator of damage accumulation for lay-ups whose behaviour is matrix-dominated as discussed in [3]. For composites that exhibit significant fibre rotation or a creep response due to a sustained positive mean stress during cycling loading, the mean strain is more meaningful for describing the fatigue degradation process than the stiffness [3] [13]. The mean strain $\epsilon_{\text{mean}}(N)$ can be calculated on each cycle N from the stress-strain loops such as $\epsilon_{\text{mean}}(N) = (\epsilon_{\text{max}}(N) + \epsilon_{\text{min}}(N))/2$. Thus, a similar expression for the accumulated damage $d(N)$ can be obtained from the value of $\epsilon_{\text{mean}}(N)$ on each cycle:

$$d(N) = \frac{\epsilon_{\text{mean}}(N) - \epsilon_{\text{mean}}(0)}{\epsilon_{\text{mean}}(N_f) - \epsilon_{\text{mean}}(0)} \quad (1)$$

where $\epsilon_{\text{mean}}(0)$ and $\epsilon_{\text{mean}}(N_f)$ are the initial and final mean strain, respectively. This definition also ensures that the damage variable $d(N)$ varies in the range from 0 to 1. From this definition, it is therefore possible to compare the changes in damage accumulation during fatigue tests.

In both materials, damage grows more rapidly as applied stress increase. The effect of frequency depends on both the applied stress level and the studied material. In C/PPS laminates, a low frequency seems to accelerate damage accumulation at high stress levels. At intermediate stress level (50%), a low frequency seems to slow down damage accumulation. At low stress level, it appears that frequency has virtually no influence. In addition, early damage (after a thousand cycles) is much more important at low frequency, which is also true in the case of Epoxy-based laminates. In C/Epoxy laminates, a high frequency seems to precipitate dramatically damage accumulation at high stress levels, whereas it seems to slow down it at low stress level. The curves representing accumulated damage $d(N)$ suggest that the fatigue behaviour can be divided into three primary stages (See Fig.5):

- During the first stage, the fatigue behaviour of AP laminates is dominated by fibres bundles rotation coming along with plastic deformation of the matrix. After a few loading phases at the

maximum stress level, damage accumulates rapidly under the form of microcracks which may initiate in multiple locations (particularly in epoxy matrix), but preferably at the interfaces between fibres and matrix in the crimp region. In C/PPS laminates, the highly ductile behaviour promotes the plasticization which comes along with a significant rotation of fibres (See Fig.4). Depending on the applied stress, such rotation leads therefore to early cracking which is more noticeable in epoxy-based laminates whose ductile behaviour is less important than in C/PPS laminates. Intra- and inter-bundles splitting also occur in +/- 45° fibres during this stage.

- The second stage is characterized by a steady damage growth rate and little damage accumulation, which increase as the applied stress increases. Once damage is initiated in crimp regions, it slowly propagates at each cycle. In C/PPS laminates, the highly ductile behaviour of the PPS matrix at $T > T_g$ delays the onset of matrix cracks at the interface and slows down their propagation. In C/Epoxy laminates, matrix and fibre/matrix interface cracking start early because of its low ductility. During this stage, the steady damage growth rate can be associated with cyclic creep strains accordingly to the conclusions drawn in [18] [19].
- During the last stage, debonding and interlaminar cracks generalize rapidly during the last stage ultimately resulting in extensive delamination, and fibre bundles pull-out in Epoxy-based laminates as well as breakage of rotated fibres at 1Hz. From the edge views of failed specimens, it appears that delamination is more extensive in C/Epoxy than in C/PPS, because the onset of cracking is earlier, and fibres pull-out is much more important. Such damage mechanisms are exacerbated at high frequency in epoxy-based laminates. They are therefore much more detrimental from the fatigue behaviour standpoint, since the fatigue life goes from 126400 cycles to 4822 cycles (-96% - See Fig.3), at 1Hz and 10 Hz respectively.

The present damage mechanisms analysis is based on the fracture surfaces after fatigue failure and on the monotonic damage chronology which proved to be close to the chronology followed during fatigue tests.

Fig.5. Changes in the damage accumulation $d(N)$ in C/PPS (a) and C/Epoxy (b) laminates during fatigue tests depending on tests frequency and applied stress level

In the present work, the damage accumulation model developed by Mao et al has been used to describe the degradation of composite materials [20]. A nonlinear function depending on the number of cycles N is proposed to capture the three primary stages of fatigue damage accumulation in composite materials subject to fatigue loading, as described above:

$$d(N) = q \left(\frac{n}{N}\right)^{m_1} + (1 - q) \left(\frac{n}{N}\right)^{m_2} \quad (2)$$

where $d(N)$ is the normalized accumulated damage; q , m_1 and m_2 are material dependent parameters; N is the current number of cycles; and N_f is the fatigue life at the corresponding applied load level.

	C/PPS		C/Epoxy	
	1 Hz	10 Hz	1 Hz	10 Hz
m_1	0.24	0.31	0.09	0.60
m_2	41.17	2.86	44.38	158.75
q	0.63	0.33	0.81	0.40

Table 1. Changes in the damage accumulation $d(N)$ in C/PPS (a) and C/Epoxy (b) laminates during fatigue tests depending on tests frequency and applied stress level

The characteristics of fast damage accumulation during the first few cycles can be captured with the first term, with $m_1 < 0$. The second term shows the fast damage growth at the end of fatigue life with $m_2 > 1$. Parameters of the proposed model are obtained with experimental data, and reported in Table 1. It's worth noticing that these parameters depend on testing frequency, but not on the applied stress. With the obtained parameters, the proposed model has been used to predict the fatigue damage accumulation in C/PPS and C/Epoxy laminates subjected to tensile loadings at different frequencies. The comparison of experimental and modelling results shows that the present damage accumulation accurately represents the damage growth during both the early and final stages of life in C/PPS laminates (See Fig.6a). However, it seems to be less predictive to represent the accumulated damage in C/Epoxy laminates (See Fig.6b). These diagrams are presented for a frequency of 1Hz but the conclusions are also available at 10Hz.

Fig.6. Model vs experimental damage accumulation in C/PPS (a) and C/Epoxy (b) laminates during fatigue tests depending on applied stress level at 1Hz

From the present analysis of the fatigue behaviour of AP laminates, it turns out that the presence of matrix-rich regions resulting from the non-planar interply structure of woven plies, ductility and

time-dependent behaviour of polymer matrix (exacerbated at $T > T_g$) are instrumental in ruling the fatigue behaviour of woven-ply PMCs. Thus, the fatigue behaviour of PPS-based laminates at $T > T_g$ is primarily due to fibre reorientation coming along with plastic deformation of the matrix during loading phase, as well as the disorientation of fibres and the viscoelastic response of the matrix during unloading phase (particularly at low frequency), rather than to fatigue damage accumulation. On the contrary, the fatigue behaviour of Epoxy-based laminates at $T < T_g$ is primarily due to fatigue damage accumulation. The reduction of stress intensities in the matrix due to more or less plasticization may delay the initiation-propagation of matrix cracks, the debonding at the fibre/matrix interface, ultimately resulting in an extension of the fatigue life. The next section will investigate to what extent the matrix-dominated behaviour of the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies contributes to modify the fatigue behaviour of QI laminates.

4 QI laminates

Contrary to the A-P lay-up, QI laminates have a fibre-dominated behaviour under monotonic as well as for a cyclical loading. Likewise the non-planar structure of fabric reinforcement is characterized by lots of matrix-rich regions, which also play an important role in the fatigue behaviour, and more specifically in the damage chronology. This section intends to show to what extent the matrix ductility will influence the damage accumulation through these regions.

4.1 General standpoint

QI lay-ups are characterized by a quasi-linear behaviour for both materials since virtually 75% of the load is borne by the 0° fibres. The overall views of stress-strain diagrams during fatigue life show that the hysteresis loops also display an elastic brittle behaviour (See Fig.7). It's also noteworthy that frequency doesn't seem to influence the loop shape. From a general standpoint, frequency proved to have different effect on the fatigue life of both materials (see Fig.8). In the case of C/PPS, an increase in frequency results in a decrease in the fatigue life. On the contrary, specimens tested at low frequency fail faster at high frequency in the case of C/Epoxy laminates.

Fig.7. Influence of frequency on fatigue life of QI C/PPS (a) and C/Epoxy (b) laminates subjected to tensile fatigue loadings at 120°C and 80% σ_u

The results corresponding to 90% σ_u have to be considered carefully because of a significant standard deviation on the number of cycles to failure. The C/PPS fatigue test at 70% σ_u and 1 Hz still must be performed, however the previous observations suggest there will be no failure before 1 million cycles. The temperature increase was negligible (no more than 20°C), and has a limited effect on the fatigue behaviour.

Fig.8. Influence of frequency on fatigue life of QI laminates subjected to fatigue tensile loadings at 120°C

4.2 Fatigue damage development analysis

Damage mechanisms can be investigated from a fracture surface analysis. The fatigue damage scenario seems to highly depend on the maximum

applied stress and on the frequency. A more precise analysis has been performed on specimens after a fatigue test for a maximum applied stress of 80% of σ_u for 10 Hz and both materials (Fig.9 & Fig.10). This analysis will provide precise pieces of information about the damage mechanisms responsible for the specimen fracture.

Fig.9. Fracture surface analysis (top and side views) of C/PPS laminates subjected to tensile fatigue loadings at 120°C, $\sigma_{max} = 80\% \sigma_u$ and 1 Hz

More specifically, on the one hand, C/PPS laminates show “brush”-like fracture surfaces with broken 0° and 45° bare fibres in hackles configuration at the specimen’s centre at both frequencies. Top and side views also indicate an extensive pull-out of 45° fibre bundles, and the onset of delamination at the specimen’s front and edges (See Fig. 9). Low frequency fracture surfaces clearly displays more 45° fibre bundles than the high frequency ones, suggesting a more significant contribution of 45° plies to the load transfer, and load bearing abilities when the first 0° fibres fail. This mechanism comes along with a more extensive delamination, and a moderate necking area in the fracture area, due to a rotation of 45° fibres just before failure. These differences can be explained by a relatively “slow” loading rate at 1 Hz compared to 10 Hz, hence justifying that viscous mechanisms can be activated at 1 Hz in the PPS rich matrix regions. Thus, it’s worth recalling that the test temperature (120°C) is higher

than the PPS' T_g . In such conditions, fibre bundles rotate during the tensile loading, resulting in an extensive debonding from the upper and lower plies. The edge views also show a very limited damage area around the fracture surface at both frequencies.

Fig.10. Fracture surface analysis (top and side views) of C/Epoxy laminates subjected to tensile fatigue loadings at 120°C , $\sigma_{\max}=80\% \sigma_u$ and 1Hz

On the other hand, C/Epoxy surface fractures display an extensive pull-out of broken bare fibre bundles through the thickness. Such damage comes along with an important delamination, and perfectly debonded plies which highlight the reinforcement architecture, especially at 10Hz (See Fig. 10). According to the failed specimens' edge views, damage (mostly interply debonding and delamination) extend in the whole specimen far from the fracture surface. It indicates a gradual scenario of damage accumulation by intraply and interply growth during the fatigue loading. At lower frequencies (1 Hz), a similar damage scenario can be observed (see Fig.10) with the same type of mechanisms (interply and intraply debonding). However, the damage area seems to be much more localized around the fracture area with a few interply debonding along the specimen's surface. The difference between the two frequencies can be explained by a localized plasticization of the matrix, which is more likely to occur in the rich resin areas at low frequency.

From these macroscopic observations, it can be concluded that the two materials are subjected to two specific damage scenarios. Therefore, several fatigue tests have been performed and stopped at different stages of the fatigue life. These tests were carried out at 80% of σ_{ult} and 10 Hz, to find a compromise between a long fatigue life and a reduced duration. For each specimen, two longitudinal and transversal cuts were made to investigate the damage accumulation in the material. However, the microscopic observations views (not presented in the paper) allowed the authors to represent the different scenarios on CAO views of both laminates (Fig.11).

In C/PPS, the early life (Fig.11-b) is characterized by the onset of a few longitudinal and transversal yarn cracks due to the coalescence of localized fibre/matrix debonding in $\pm 45^{\circ}$ plies. Longitudinal and transversal cracks (observed on the fracture surfaces – Fig.9) also appear at the specimen surface during the first stage. The subsequent stage (Fig.11-c) are characterized by a generalization of the intrayarn cracks as well as the onset of intralaminar cracks in 45° plies due to the coalescence of the yarn cracks. During the last stage of fatigue life (Fig.11-d), propagation of the intralaminar cracks along the weft and the warp fibres interface can be observed, as well as some “meta-delamination” in $0/90^{\circ}$ plies and very localized edge effects, ultimately failure is associated with the breakage of 0° fibres. Even at 90% of fatigue life, there are only a few intralaminar cracks, confirming what was observed on the fracture surface (Fig.9). However, it's worth noticing that no matrix cracking occurs, confirming the important role of the rich matrix areas in the fatigue damage accumulation because they act as cracks barrier [9].

Damage onset occurs a lot slower in C/Epoxy than C/PPS laminates. Besides, damage is localized in the outer plies. Indeed, at 20% of fatigue life (Fig.11-b), limited damage can be observed in both views: matrix cracking (contrary to C/PPS laminates) and intralaminar and interlaminar debonding initiating at the crack tips. Later, specimens experienced the growth of intra and interlaminar cracking at the vicinity of 45° plies (Fig.11-c). This stage is also characterized by the onset of longitudinal and transversal intrayarn cracks in the 45° plies. During the next stage a generalization of interlaminar cracks and of delamination can be observed in the whole specimen. At the end of fatigue life (Fig.11-d),

delamination extends extensively in the whole specimen making impossible the load transfer between the plies and locally leading to high overstresses. Thus, some 0° fibre bundles rapidly break, which is followed by a catastrophic failure of specimen coming along with the pull-out of 45° fibre bundles and the breakage of remaining 0° fibres. Both views are evidence supporting an important interaction between the different damage modes.

Finally, the damage scenarios and the failure mechanisms are very different in both materials. C/Epoxy laminates are very sensitive to interlaminar cracking which leads to delamination according to gradual damage scenario and C/PPS laminates display a rather catastrophic fatigue behaviour, close to the one observed when they are subjected to monotonic loadings. Depending on the matrix behaviour (very ductile and time-dependent at 120°C in PPS, and brittle in Epoxy), matrix is more or less prone to cracking. This is particularly true in rich matrix regions where the localized plasticity results in an enhanced toughness. These regions therefore act as cracks barriers by delaying their onset and slowing down their growth, confirming the work conclusions drawn in [9] [11].

The scenarios for lower frequencies (1Hz) can be determined. In both materials, the slower loading rate allows the matrix viscous mechanisms to be activated. In C/PPS as well as C/Epoxy, viscous mechanisms (e.g. viscoelasticity - viscoplasticity) will significantly influence damage accumulation through localized plasticization in the rich matrix area, delaying and minimizing matrix cracking. In C/PPS, the 45° plies plasticization will cause progressive interply and intraply debonding. The generalization of damage in this area will cause premature 0° fibre bundle breakage, allowing the 45° to bear a larger part of the load and a limited fibre rotation. In C/Epoxy, the activated viscous mechanisms will enhance the local toughness of the material and the rich-resin region will act as barrier for cracks, preventing cracks propagation to the whole specimen.

Fig.11. Damage accumulation in C/PPS and C/Epoxy laminates subjected to tensile fatigue loadings at 120°C $\sigma_{max}=80\% \sigma_{ult}$ and 10Hz at pristine state (a), 20% (b), 50% (c) and 90% (d) of fatigue life.

4.3 Fatigue damage development analysis

Damage scenarios have to be related to the damage accumulation concept, explained in 3.3. Contrary to the A-P laminates, the stiffness loss is a suitable parameter to evaluate the damage accumulation. A similar equation to (1) can be used:

$$d(N) = \frac{E_0 - E(N)}{E_0 - E_f} \quad (3)$$

where E_0 and E_f are the initial and final stiffness, respectively.

Fig.12. Damage accumulation vs number of cycles in C/PPS and C/Epoxy laminates subjected to tensile fatigue loadings at 120°C $\sigma_{max}=80\% \sigma_{ult}$ and 10Hz

The damage accumulation vs number of cycles curves for C/PPS and C/Epoxy during a fatigue test at 80 % σ_u and 10 Hz is shown on Fig.12. According to the damage scenarios evidenced by microscopic observations at different stages of fatigue life, the four damage states schematically illustrated for each material have been reported on this damage accumulation diagram (see Fig.12).

As it was observed for the A-P laminates, these curves suggest that the fatigue behaviour can be divided into three primary stages:

- During the first stage, damage initiates and accumulates relatively rapidly after a few cycles. In C/PPS, longitudinal and transversal intrayarn cracks. Such cracking comes along with the plasticization of the rich resin area preventing the onset of matrix cracks. The simultaneous damage initiation in the whole specimen results in a relatively rapid loss of stiffness modulus. In C/Epoxy, the damage accumulation is much slower, and consists of matrix cracking, propagating at the ply interface of 45° plies.
- The second stage is characterized by a slower gradual damage accumulation that seems to increase with the applied stress. The gradual change in damage is in agreement with the growth and the generalization of cracks in the materials. Such growth corresponds to the coalescence of intrayarn cracks leading to intralaminar and interlaminar cracks in C/PPS laminates. Because of the local plasticization of rich resin areas, the crack path is scattered with barriers to its growth, making it slower. On the contrary, intralaminar cracks propagate rather freely across the matrix area and along the plies interfaces in the C/Epoxy laminates. Moreover, the over stresses induced at the cracks tips in these areas, lead to intrayarn cracking in both directions.
- During the last stage, a fast damage growth can be observed. This phase lasts only a few cycles and illustrates a sudden breakage of 0° fibres for the C/PPS laminates. Failure results from the generalization of damage and the transfer of load coming from the 0° fibres when they break. On the contrary, this stage seems to be much more gradual and displays an inflexion point corresponding to an increase in the damage accumulation rate for the C/Epoxy laminates. At this point, damage is already extensively spread throughout the laminates,

especially at the plies interfaces. Extensive delamination leads to locally high overstresses. Thus, some 0° fibre bundles rapidly break resulting in the catastrophic failure of specimens, especially the pull-out of 45° fibre bundles and the breakage of 0° plies.

At low frequencies, the damage accumulation scenario is virtually the same. The only exception is the enhanced effect of matrix viscous mechanisms compared to 10 Hz tests, resulting in a local plasticization of the resin especially in the rich matrix areas.

Conclusion

The present work was aimed at investigating the influence of the matrix behaviour on the tension-tension fatigue behaviour of woven-ply TP- and TS-based laminates at test temperatures such as: $T_g|_{C/PPS} < T < T_g|_{Epoxy}$. Thus, matrix ductile and time-dependent behaviours (e.g. viscoelasticity and viscoplasticity) are exacerbated at $T > T_g$. Besides, the fatigue behaviour of composite system seems to be closely associated with the presence of matrix-rich regions, resulting from the non-planar interply structure of the woven plies. These areas are instrumental in modifying the damage chronology and the fatigue behaviour of A-P laminates, but also in ruling the fatigue behaviour of QI laminates, due to the response of $\pm 45^\circ$ plies.

Based on microscopic observations (at different stages of fatigue life) and fracture surface analysis, two different damage scenarios were determined in QI laminates.

On the one hand, C/PPS laminates display a rather catastrophic fatigue failure (0° fibre bundles breakage) with no preliminary sign of failure. Damage consists of several longitudinal and transversal intrayarn cracks in 45° plies, followed by their coalescence in several intralaminar and interlaminar cracks and some delamination on specimens' edges. The microscopic observations did not reveal any matrix cracks. Indeed, PPS matrix is locally highly ductile ($T > T_g$) which delays cracking onset through a localized plasticization. This phenomenon seems to increase material toughness, and acts as cracks barriers in matrix-rich regions.

On the other hand, C/Epoxy laminates display a gradual failure dominated by debonding and delamination. Damage is initiated in matrix rich areas and propagates throughout specimen by

matrix cracking, intralaminar and interlaminar debonding, ultimately resulting in extensive delamination. Because of a brittle behaviour ($T < T_g$), matrix cracking occurs early in matrix-rich regions during fatigue life, leading to a generalized damage state in the whole material.

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